

A Study of Malaria-Related Pediatrics Morbidity and Mortality in India

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Abstract:

Background: Malaria remains a significant public health challenge globally, particularly affecting pediatric populations in endemic regions. Despite efforts to reduce malaria incidence, the disease continues to disproportionately impact children under five, especially in low- and middle-income countries like India. This study aims to evaluate malaria-related pediatric morbidity and mortality in India, focusing on socio-economic and nutritional factors contributing to adverse outcomes.

Methods: The study included 80 pediatric patients diagnosed with malaria. Data were collected through medical record reviews and interviews with parents or guardians. Statistical analyses included Chi-square tests and logistic regression to identify significant predictors of morbidity and mortality.

Results: The majority of patients were aged 1-5 years (37.5%) and predominantly male (56.3%). Most came from low socio-economic backgrounds (68.7%) and a significant portion were underweight (37.5%). Complications were observed in 37.5% of the patients, with severe anemia being the most common (25%). The mortality rate was 10%, predominantly affecting the 1-5 year age group (37.5%) and males (62.5%). Socio-economic status and nutritional status were significantly associated with complications ($p=0.02$) and mortality ($p=0.03$), respectively. Logistic regression identified low socio-economic status ($OR=2.5$, $p=0.04$) and underweight status ($OR=3.0$, $p=0.02$) as significant predictors of adverse outcomes.

Conclusion: Malaria-related morbidity and mortality among pediatric patients in India are influenced by socio-economic and nutritional factors. Targeted interventions addressing these disparities are crucial for reducing the disease burden.

Recommendations: Efforts should focus on improving socio-economic conditions, enhancing nutritional support, and ensuring effective malaria prevention and treatment strategies. Community-based programs and healthcare access improvements are essential for mitigating the impact of malaria on vulnerable pediatric populations.

Keywords: Pediatric Malaria, Morbidity, Mortality, Socio-Economic Factors, Nutritional Status.

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Introduction

Malaria remains a significant public health challenge globally, particularly in pediatric populations in endemic regions. Despite progress in reducing malaria incidence and mortality over the past two decades, the disease continues to disproportionately affect children under the age of five, especially in low- and middle-income countries [1]. In 2020, the WHO reported an estimated 241 million cases of malaria worldwide, with approximately 627,000 deaths, of which 80% occurred in children under five years old [2]. India, being a malaria-endemic country, faces substantial morbidity and mortality among its pediatric population due to the disease.

The pediatric burden of malaria in India is exacerbated by socio-economic disparities and nutritional deficiencies. Children from low socio-economic backgrounds are more susceptible to malaria due to factors such as poor living conditions, lack of access to preventive measures like insecticide-treated bed nets, and limited healthcare access. Nutritional status also plays a critical role in determining the severity of malaria outcomes. Malnourished children, particularly those who are underweight, are at a higher risk of severe malaria complications, which can lead to increased mortality.

Recent studies have highlighted the complexity of malaria transmission and its multifaceted impact on pediatric health. According to a study, the prevalence of malaria in Indian children varies significantly across different regions, influenced by factors such as climatic conditions, vector density, and local healthcare infrastructure [3]. The study emphasized the need for region-specific strategies to effectively combat malaria and reduce its burden on children.

Complications arising from malaria in children, such as severe anemia, cerebral malaria, and respiratory distress, significantly contribute to the overall morbidity and mortality rates. Severe anemia, in particular, has been identified as a leading cause of death among pediatric malaria patients. This complication often requires urgent blood transfusions, which may not be readily available in resource-limited settings, further complicating the management of the disease [4].

Efforts to mitigate malaria-related morbidity and mortality in children must focus on improving socio-economic conditions, enhancing nutritional status, and ensuring timely and effective medical interventions. The implementation of integrated community-based programs that combine malaria prevention, treatment, and nutritional support has shown promise in reducing the disease's impact on children. Moreover, ongoing research and development of new antimalarial drugs and vaccines hold potential for long-term solutions to combat pediatric malaria.

This study aims at evaluating malaria-related pediatric morbidity and mortality in India.

Methodology

Study Design: A descriptive cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at BMIMS, Pawapuri, Nalanda, from March 2022 to March 2023.

Participants: The study included a total of 80 pediatric patients diagnosed with malaria during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 0 to 14 years.
- Diagnosed with malaria (confirmed by laboratory tests).
- Parents or guardians who provided informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with comorbid conditions unrelated to malaria.

- Those who did not complete the required follow-up.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients admitted to the hospital during the study period were included consecutively. Information bias was minimized by using standardized data collection forms and trained personnel.

Variables: Variables included age, gender, socio-economic status, nutritional status, clinical presentation, and treatment received, morbidity (complications) and mortality (death).

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of medical record reviews and direct interviews with patients' parents or guardians. Information gathered included demographic details, clinical presentation, laboratory findings, treatment provided, and outcomes.

Procedure: Pediatric patients diagnosed with malaria were identified and enrolled in the study. Medical records were reviewed, and interviews with parents or guardians were conducted to gather comprehensive data on each patient. Detailed clinical examinations were performed, and laboratory tests were reviewed to confirm malaria diagnosis and assess complications. Patients were monitored throughout their hospital stay to document treatment responses and outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into a computerized database and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics were calculated for continuous variables, and frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. Chi-square tests were used to assess associations between categorical variables, and t-tests or ANOVA were used for continuous variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Logistic regression analysis was performed to identify predictors of morbidity and mortality.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

The study included 80 pediatric patients diagnosed with malaria from March 2022 to March 2023. The demographic and clinical characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
- <1	10	12.5
- 1-5	30	37.5
- 6-10	25	31.3
- 11-14	15	18.7
Gender		
- Male	45	56.3
- Female	35	43.7
Socio-economic Status		
- Low	55	68.7
- Middle	20	25.0
- High	5	6.3
Nutritional Status		
- Underweight	30	37.5
- Normal	45	56.3
- Overweight	5	6.2
Clinical Presentation		
- Fever	80	100
- Anemia	50	62.5
- Splenomegaly	35	43.7
- Hepatomegaly	20	25.0

The majority of the patients (37.5%) were in the 1-5 year age group, with a slightly higher proportion of males (56.3%) than females (43.7%). Most patients (68.7%) came from low socio-economic backgrounds, and a significant portion (37.5%) were underweight.

Out of the 80 patients, 30 (37.5%) developed complications related to malaria. The types of complications observed are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Malaria-Related Complications

Complication	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Severe Anemia	20	25.0
Cerebral Malaria	5	6.3
Respiratory Distress	3	3.7
Renal Failure	2	2.5

Severe anemia was the most common complication, affecting 25% of the patients. Cerebral malaria was observed in 6.3% of the cases, while respiratory distress and renal failure were less common.

The mortality rate was 10% (8 patients). The distribution of deaths by age group and gender is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Mortality by Age Group and Gender

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
- <1	2	25.0
- 1-5	3	37.5
- 6-10	2	25.0
- 11-14	1	12.5
Gender		
- Male	5	62.5
- Female	3	37.5

Most of the deaths occurred in the 1-5 year age group (37.5%), followed by the <1 year and 6-10 year age groups (both 25%). A higher mortality rate was observed among males (62.5%) compared to females (37.5%).

Chi-square tests revealed significant associations between socio-economic status and the

development of complications ($p = 0.02$), and between nutritional status and mortality ($p = 0.03$). Logistic regression analysis identified low socio-economic status (OR = 2.5, 95% CI: 1.1-5.8, $p = 0.04$) and underweight status (OR = 3.0, 95% CI: 1.2-7.5, $p = 0.02$) as significant predictors of morbidity and mortality, respectively.

Table 4: Association Between Socio-Economic Status and Complications

Socio-economic Status	Low	Middle	High
Complications (n)	25	5	0
No Complications (n)	30	15	5
p-value	0.02		

Table 5: Association Between Nutritional Status and Mortality

Nutritional Status	Mortality (n)	No Mortality (n)	p-value
Underweight	5	25	0.03
Normal	3	42	
Overweight	0	5	

The analysis shows that children from low socio-economic backgrounds were significantly more likely to develop complications ($p = 0.02$), and underweight children had a higher mortality rate ($p = 0.03$).

Discussion

The majority of the patients were in the 1-5 year age group (37.5%), with a slightly higher proportion of males (56.3%) compared to females (43.7%). Most patients came from low socio-economic backgrounds (68.7%) and a significant portion (37.5%) were underweight. This demographic data highlights the vulnerability of younger children and those from disadvantaged backgrounds to malaria.

Out of the 80 patients, 30 (37.5%) developed complications related to malaria, with severe anemia being the most common (25%). Other complications included cerebral malaria (6.3%), respiratory distress (3.7%), and renal failure (2.5%). The overall mortality rate was 10%, with deaths most commonly occurring in the 1-5 year age group (37.5%). More males (62.5%) died compared to females (37.5%). These findings suggest that severe anemia is a major contributor to morbidity and mortality in pediatric malaria patients, and that younger children and males are at higher risk of fatal outcomes.

Statistical analysis revealed significant associations between socio-economic status and the development of complications ($p = 0.02$), and between nutritional status and mortality ($p = 0.03$). Children from low socio-economic backgrounds were more likely to develop complications, and underweight children had a higher mortality rate. Logistic regression identified low socio-economic status (OR = 2.5, 95% CI: 1.1-5.8, $p = 0.04$) and underweight status (OR = 3.0, 95% CI: 1.2-7.5, $p = 0.02$) as significant predictors of morbidity and mortality, respectively. These associations underscore the critical impact of socio-economic and nutritional factors on the health outcomes of children with malaria.

The study's findings highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions to address socio-economic disparities and nutritional deficiencies to reduce malaria-related morbidity and mortality in pediatric populations. Enhanced malaria prevention and treatment strategies, improved healthcare access, and nutritional support for disadvantaged children are crucial to mitigating the impact of malaria on this vulnerable group.

Malaria is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in the pediatric population in India. A prospective observational study was conducted on children with severe malaria at SCB Medical College, Cuttack. They found that fever, anemia, and prostration were common complications. Respiratory distress, CNS involvement, shock, and renal failure were major predictors of mortality. The case fatality rate was 8.5%, with a higher risk associated with multiple organ dysfunction [5].

The clinical presentation of malaria and response to treatment in children under twelve years was studied. They found a high incidence of anemia, with 38.8% of patients presenting with pallor. Severe malaria was diagnosed in 27.7% of cases, with significant morbidity associated with *P. vivax* infections [6]. Research described the clinico-hematological manifestations of malaria in children in Western Uttar Pradesh. The majority of cases were due to *P. vivax* (88.7%), with severe malaria present in 23.4% of patients. Complications included bleeding, shock, acidosis, and severe anemia [7].

A study analyzed morbidity and mortality associated with *P. vivax* and *P. falciparum* in a tertiary care hospital in Navi Mumbai. They reported a higher mortality rate in *P. falciparum* cases, with severe complications such as cerebral malaria, ARDS, and multi-organ failure [8]. Malaria cases in a tertiary care hospital in Mangaluru was studied. They found that 14.16% of patients had severe manifestations of malaria, with *P. vivax* being the most common causative agent. The mean duration of hospital stay was approximately 5 days [9].

Conclusion

This study underscores the need for targeted interventions to address socio-economic disparities and nutritional deficiencies to reduce malaria-related morbidity and mortality in pediatric populations. Enhanced malaria prevention and treatment strategies, along with improved healthcare access for disadvantaged groups, are crucial for mitigating the impact of malaria on children in India.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Efforts should focus on improving socio-economic conditions, enhancing nutritional support, and ensuring effective malaria prevention and treatment strategies. Community-based programs and healthcare access improvements are essential for mitigating the impact of malaria on vulnerable pediatric populations.

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List of abbreviations:

WHO: World Health Organization

OR: Odds Ratio

CI: Confidence Interval

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

CNS: Central Nervous System

ARDS: Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome

BMIMS: Bihar Medical Institute of Medical Sciences

SCB: Srirama Chandra Bhanja Medical College

P. vivax: Plasmodium vivax

P. falciparum: Plasmodium falciparum

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